

29-01-2026

Deliverable 1.5

Data Management Plan and Data Policy (Final)

Contractual Date:	31.01.2026
Actual Date:	29-01-2026
Grant Agreement No.:	101095055
Work Package:	WP1
Task Item:	Task 4
Nature of Deliverable:	DMP (Data Management Plan)
Dissemination Level:	PU (Public)
Lead Partner:	DeiC
Document ID:	SUBMERSE: DMP
Authors:	Hannah Mihai (DeiC); Rene Belsø (DeiC); Chris Atherton (GÉANT)

Abstract

This document is the final Data Management Plan of the SUBMERSE project. It describes the Data Management practices and policies as developed throughout the duration of the project.

Funded by
the European Union

© European Future Innovation System Centre on behalf of the SUBMERSE project. The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101095055 (SUBMERSE).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	Person
0.1	18-12-25	First draft issued	H. Mihai, R. Belsø, C. Atherton
0.2	08-01-26	Quality review	M. Barberis
0.3	16-01-26	Review	O. Schjelderup, M. Als Pedersen, F. Tilmann, A. Strollo, M. Loureiro, C. Evangelidis
1.0	29-01-26	Final Revisions and Submission	H. Mihai, M. Barberis

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	2
2 SUBMERSE Data Policies	3
3 SUBMERSE Data Summary	4
3.1 Madeira	7
3.2 Sines	7
3.3 Svalbard and Ny Ålesund	8
3.4 Preveza - Crotone	9
3.5 Rhodes	9
4 Data Access	10
4.1 Trusted Research Environment	10
4.2 Inter buffer data access	10
4.3 Open buffer	11
5 Status of Use Cases	12
5.1 Geoscientific Use Cases	12
5.2 Oceanographic Use Cases	13
5.3 Marine Biology Use Cases	14
6 FAIR Data in the SUBMERSE project	15
6.1 Making Data Findable (F)	15
6.2 Making Data Accessible (A)	16
6.3 Making Data Interoperable (I)	17
6.4 Making Data Reusable (R)	17
6.5 SUBMERSE data FAIRification Conclusions	18
7 Other Research Outputs	19
7.1 Training Materials	19

7.2	Software	19
7.3	Scientific Publications	20
7.4	Data emerging from Project Management	20
8	Data Security	22
9	SUBMERSE Ethics	23
10	SUBMERSE outlook and final remarks	24
Appendix A	[Site Status]	25
A.1	Crotone	25
A.2	Preveza	25
A.3	Rhodes	26
A.4	Sines	26
A.5	Madeira	27
A.6	Longyearbyen	27
A.7	Ny Ålesund	28
A.8	Zandvoort	28

List of Figures

Figure 1: Data flows: Ingest → Process → Persist → Retain → Dispose	4
Figure 2: Map of data collection sites	6
Figure 3: Template for site status	6

List of Tables

Table 1: Object Key Structure and minimum required metadata fields	5
--	---

Executive Summary

This Data Management Plan outlines the principles, workflows, and responsibilities guiding the management of Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS), transponder based State of Polarisation (SOP), polarimeter based SOP, Radio Frequency Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (RF OTDR), SOP OTDR, and derived datasets produced within SUBMERSE, a Horizon Europe project developing a novel research instrument based on live submarine fibre-optic communication cables. Data management practices across the participating sites in Norway, Greece, and Portugal reflect varying operational contexts, sensitivities, and infrastructure ownership, resulting in different degrees of FAIR implementation. While raw data often remain locally stored due to security, privacy, and contractual constraints, all partners follow community standards (e.g., HDF5 for full resolution, miniSEED for decimated data, metadata following DAS-RCN recommendations) and progressively assign DOIs and publish derived datasets in open repositories when permissible. The project also develops machine-learning-based software tools, training materials, and a growing set of scientific publications and dataset releases. Throughout the project, strong emphasis is placed on ethics and security, with sensitive information removed prior to data sharing, site-specific policies implemented, and non-public security deliverables guiding best practices. Looking forward, SUBMERSE aims to increase automation, strengthen metadata harmonisation, support long-term preservation through domain repositories, and further enhance FAIRness as technical, organisational, and regulatory conditions evolve.

1 Introduction

This final Data Management Plan (DMP) for the SUBMERSE project, funded under the Horizon Europe call Next Generation of Scientific Instrumentation, Tools and Methods (HORIZON-INFRA-2022-TECH-01), presents the overall strategies, procedures, and outcomes related to data handling resulting from work done throughout the project's lifecycle. This Document is building on the work presented in the initial version of the Data Management Plan¹ submitted at the beginning of the project. This document captures the evolution of data handling practices throughout the projects lifetime and reflects adjustments made or to be made. SUBMERSE set out to design, implement, and validate a novel research instrument that leverages existing ocean-floor telecommunications fibre optic infrastructure as a large-scale sensing platform. By integrating submarine fibre optic communication cables operated by National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) with the data distribution capacities of EPOS-ERIC² and the Copernicus Marine Service³, the project has developed an innovative, multi-infrastructure solution, now capable of generating and disseminating high-value environmental data.

Through close collaboration between numerous European partners with data collection sites in Portugal, Greece and Norway, SUBMERSE has demonstrated the feasibility of acquiring and distributing Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS), transponder-based State of Polarisation (SOP), polarimeter-based SOP, Radio Frequency Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (RF OTDR), and SOP OTDR data streams from operational telecommunication fibre systems. The resulting infrastructure supports the production of temporal and geographically diverse datasets of significant scientific relevance, enabling new insights into marine geohazards, oceanographic processes, and seismic phenomena. The projects data management supported new scientific instrumentation, methods, and tools by establishing new technologies, services, and community-relevant long-term datasets.

This DMP documents the data landscape of SUBMERSE. It provides an overview of the project's data collection sites, the types and volumes of data acquired, and the processing and curation workflows developed to pursue interoperable access and long-term data preservation. It outlines how the project has worked to implement the FAIR principles⁴ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) across all stages of data production and distribution, ensuring best possible compliance with Horizon Europe requirements and alignment with the policies of associated research infrastructures. SUBMERSE data management has, when time and resources allowed, worked to take onboard the EOSC Interoperability Framework while recognising that more work needs to be done. In addition, the DMP addresses the ethical, legal, and security considerations associated with collecting and disseminating data from commercial telecommunication assets, including issues of privacy, confidentiality, and data stewardship.

Finally, this document reflects on the technical and organisational challenges encountered during the development of the SUBMERSE instrument and highlights the solutions adopted to ensure robust data management. It concludes with an outlook on future work, describing opportunities for continued development, broader international integration, and the long-term exploitation of data yet to be gathered based on future improvements of the fibre optic sensing technologies explored and created by SUBMERSE.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11065792>

² <https://www.epos-eu.org/epos-eric>

³ <https://marine.copernicus.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

2 SUBMERSE Data Policies

The SUBMERSE project operates across multiple national jurisdictions and in close collaboration with telecommunications operators including national research and education networks (NRENs), research institutions, and security concerned authorities. Because the sensing systems are deployed on operational submarine fibre-optic cables, across a multitude of jurisdictions, each data collection site requires its own tailored Data Policy. These policies define the rules, constraints, and responsibilities governing the generation, handling, and dissemination of DAS, SOP datasets. To varying degrees, the Data Policies are developed jointly by the national security agencies, cable owners, instrument owners, and the national SUBMERSE coordinators. This ensures that scientific access to data is enabled without compromising local security requirements associated with telecommunication infrastructure and data collection. Due to their sensitive content, these site-specific Data Policies are not publicly available.

Each Data Policy follows a common template that clarifies the scope of the data to be generated, the roles of the parties involved, and the details of the technical setup, including recording parameters and expected data products. The policies specify data ownership, which typically resides with the instrument operators and NRENs in collaboration with national research project leads; however, national frameworks differ and, in some cases, remain only partially defined. Metadata requirements are defined to the extent allowable under security constraints, recognising that information such as detailed cable route and landing stations may need to be generalised or withheld.

A central function of the Data Policies is to regulate the handling of real-time data flows and data buffering. Where feasible and permitted, real-time data streams—typically reduced through spatial and moderate temporal downsampling—may be distributed via the SeedLink⁵ protocol. At present, these real-time streams do not apply active scrubbing or censoring and therefore remain under restricted access. Full-resolution data are stored only temporarily in secure national data buffer facilities, where they undergo further assessment and processing in accordance with national security and data governance requirements. The policies further specify the conditions under which buffered data may be processed at protected national computing centres by security vetted researchers.

Long-term preservation applies only to scrubbed and FAIR-compliant data products (processed datasets). These are transferred to community repositories – e.g. the European Integrated Data Archive⁶ (EIDA nodes) operated by European Plate Observing System⁷ (EPOS), or other domain-specific infrastructures such as Copernicus Marine Service – following established standards for metadata, persistent identifiers, formats, and licences. SUBMERSE draws heavily on the DAS data management practices developed in Geo-INQUIRE and maintains close collaboration with EPOS, EMSO, and other research infrastructure partners to ensure alignment with emerging standards for waveform, SOP, and polarimetric data.

Through this framework of site-specific Data Policies, SUBMERSE aims to ensure that data handling is fully compliant with national security regulations while enabling wide scientific reuse once the data have been appropriately processed. The policies, therefore, provide the essential link between the protected national data environments in which the raw data originate and the open, FAIR-aligned research ecosystems where the cleaned datasets are ultimately preserved and shared.

⁵ <https://docs.fdsn.org/projects/seedlink/en/latest/protocol.html>

⁶ <https://www.orfeus-eu.org/data/eida/>

⁷ <https://www.epos-eu.org/>

3 SUBMERSE Data Summary

This section provides an overview of the data generated at each data collection site during the SUBMERSE project, including raw and processed data from Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS), State of Polarisation (SOP), polarimetry, and complementary Ocean Bottom Seismometer (OBS). It summarises data volumes, acquisition periods, streaming and processing capabilities, and access constraints arising from infrastructure operator agreements, cable ownership, and national regulatory frameworks. The descriptions emphasise the scientific value of the collected data, their relevance for long-term monitoring and multidisciplinary research, and their readiness—where permitted—for integration into European and international data distribution pathways through participating research infrastructures.

It should be noted that the value of data collected is twofold, in that the data itself might or might not have scientific value, but the ever-evolving ability to process real time data streams has value in any case. That is to say that the development of data collection and processing workflows have significant value independently of the specifics of the current data sets. Focus is more on developing instrumentation and workflows, than on the current data collected. There is an ambition to be able to process the integrators real time data streams, producing data products on the fly, from all sites, rather than analysing small data snippets of a more or less random nature, as is the case today.

SUBMERSE data originate from multiple instrument types from many sites and are produced in several formats reflecting community practices and technical requirements. The general data flow can be seen in Figure 1. Core datasets include raw DAS data in HDF5 format and derived DAS products in miniSEED, SOP and polarimetric measurements are to be processed preferentially in HDF5 and, where appropriate, in CSV, Parquet, or NetCDF formats, with associated metadata represented in JSON or YAML. In addition, operational telemetry and system logs are collected in lightweight, machine-readable formats (e.g. JSON, Prometheus-compatible metrics) to support monitoring, troubleshooting, and provenance tracking.

Figure 1: Data flows: Ingest → Process → Persist → Retain → Dispose

Data enter the SUBMERSE data ecosystem through controlled ingest paths, typically from cable landing stations or instrument sites to national or domain-specific facilities/institutes, optimally and in due cause Trusted Research Environments (TREs). Transfers are performed over secure Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) or private

links using standard protocols such as SFTP, S3, or HTTPS, with authentication and authorisation handled via service accounts based on OIDC/OAuth 2.0. Once ingested, data are stored in national MinIO object storage systems that implement a harmonised namespace and layout to ensure consistency across sites. Each national deployment maintains an “open-buffer” bucket, within which objects follow a mandatory hierarchical key structure (see Table 1) that encodes site, cable, fibre, instrument identifier, acquisition date, and filename. This convention prevents naming collisions, supports automated processing, and enables efficient downstream discovery.

Table 1: Object Key Structure and minimum required metadata fields

Field	Meaning	Example
Site	Physical site / facility	Preveza, Crotone, Zandvoort, Sines
Cable	Cable or system identifier	ionian-01, med-cable-a, local-loop-1
Fibre	Fibre ID within the cable	fp01, fp02, fpA, fpB (document per site)
instrument-id	Interrogator / instrument identifier	das-01, das-02, sop-01
YYYYMMDD	Acquisition date (ISO basic)	20251126
filename	Actual file name from the instrument / pipeline	010352.hdf5

Metadata and provenance information follow the DAS-RCN recommendations⁸ for DAS datasets and equivalent emerging standards for SOP data. Where feasible, metadata are embedded directly within HDF5 files, complemented by external metadata records. A minimum set of metadata fields, as described in Table 1, is consistently provided. Each instrument directory also contains a machine-readable README file documenting the version of the storage design specification used at the site, ensuring transparency and traceability across national implementations.

Data retention policies reflect the current state-of-affairs, i.e technological development (software/hardware) in ability to process integration data streams in real time; operational and security needs, legal obligations and economy. Raw, potentially sensitive data are held for limited periods in national TREs—typically one month. Data can be held longer, possibly up to three months in open buffers—before deletion or transfer to longer-term archives, subject to security scrubbing and partner agreements. Archived datasets may be retained for up to twelve months or longer when justified by scientific value, with legal hold and write-once-read-many (WORM) mechanisms applied where required. Access to data is generally restricted to eligible researchers during these stages and is progressively expanded. For curated, FAIR-compliant datasets distributed through domain-specific repositories, data can be kept forever, subject to repository policies.

⁸ Lai, V. H., Hodgkinson, K. M., Porritt, R. W., & Mellors, R. (2024). Toward a Metadata Standard for Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) Data Collection. *Seismological Research Letters*, 95(3), 1986–1999. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220230325>

Figure 2: Map of data collection sites

The different data collection sites (see Figure 2) have produced various amounts of data from calibration experiments and collection campaigns. Across six submarine and terrestrial-submarine fibre locations, the project installed and configured a range of Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) systems, supported in some cases by Ocean Bottom Seismometers (OBS). The overview highlights installation timelines, instrument configurations, integration with existing telecom infrastructure, and the calibration and testing campaigns carried out to ensure reliable acquisition and interoperability across the SUBMERSE network.

Each site setup follows a common template which can be seen in figure 3. The detailed site statuses for each site as of January 2026 can be found in Appendix A.

Figure 3: Template for site status

3.1 Madeira

The Madeira site represents a mature and operational long-term DAS deployment within the SUBMERSE project. An OptoDAS interrogator⁹ was installed in October 2023 on a 57 km dark-fibre pair of the Emacom/EllaLink¹⁰ submarine cable system, operating at a 10 m gauge length, 5 m spatial sampling, and a 500 Hz sampling rate, corresponding to 11,293 virtual channels. Continuous, GPS-synchronised acquisition was achieved from June 2024 onward. Calibration and performance tests conducted in 2025 included short-duration high-frequency acquisition periods at 1,000 Hz and 1,600 Hz, as well as the establishment of a real-time SeedLink¹¹ stream in May 2025, providing 20 decimated channels to Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere (IPMA). Firmware upgrades deployed in June 2025 introduced onboard decimation and spatial averaging capabilities, which improved the quality of the streamed data. Five of the twenty streamed channels are now integrated into the national seismic observation network to improve epicentral locations. Temporary network code 31 was assigned to this installation, foreseeing a continuous operation during the expected lifetime of the cable. External funding has been acquired to deploy reference sensors close to the fibre to obtain transfer functions for ground motion, temperature, and pressure.

By the end of the reporting period, the Madeira deployment had generated approximately 300 TB of sample DAS data, including a semi-continuous acquisition period spanning December 2024 to June 2025. Of this volume, around 280 TB are stored in the INESC TEC¹² MinIO¹³ object storage system, where data are buffered for several months and accessible to SUBMERSE partners under controlled conditions. An additional curated dataset of approximately 7 TB DAS data acquired in 2023, has been archived at GEOFON¹⁴ with an assigned DOI, while remaining data reside in local storage. This corresponds to one week of full-resolution DAS data, which obviously can seem small and of spatial and temporal random nature. However, there are constant improvements being made to enhance the production capacity of real-time data products. Real-time data access is still limited to the streamed channels, and broader access remains restricted pending evaluation in technology, organisation, security mitigation, economy – i.e. policy clearance. As the available buffer storage has reached capacity, routine deletion of the oldest data has commenced in accordance with the project’s retention policy.

3.2 Sines

The Sines site constitutes a major high-resolution DAS deployment within SUBMERSE, focused on performance benchmarking and calibration in an offshore, transoceanic cable environment. A C-band OptoDAS interrogator was deployed on the EllaLink trunk cable at the Sines landing station on 27 May 2025. The system is configured with a 6.1m gauge length, 1m spatial sampling, and a 1.6kHz sampling rate, yielding 53,025 virtual channels. Time synchronisation is achieved via a remotely connected time server. To characterise DAS sensitivity and validate signal fidelity, a dedicated four-month Ocean Bottom Seismometer (OBS) calibration campaign was conducted between October 2024 and February 2025. Seven broadband DEPAS¹⁵ instruments, equipped with seismometers and hydrophones, were deployed in proximity to the cable route, providing an independent reference for offshore seismic and acoustic measurements.

⁹ <https://www.asn.com/fiber-sensing/>

¹⁰ <https://ella.link/>

¹¹ Seismological and environmental data protocol: <https://docs.fdsn.org/projects/seedlink/en/draft/protocol.html>

¹² <https://www.inesctec.pt/en>

¹³ <https://www.min.io/>

¹⁴ <https://geofon.gfz.de/>

¹⁵ <https://research-infrastructure.gfz.de/en/infrastructure/42> German instrument pool for amphibian seismology (Deutscher Geräte-Pool für amphibische Seismologie)

Raw DAS acquisition at Sines has generated approximately 400 TB of sample data in HDF5¹⁶ format. In addition, a curated subset of SOP and RF-SOP measurements, totalling 51 GB and provided by Nokia in XLSX format, complements the DAS dataset. As of December 2025, all raw datasets are stored at University of Porto in the INESC TEC MinIO object storage system, with no automated pipeline yet established for transfer to external repositories. Access to the data is currently restricted to SUBMERSE project members and is managed through institutional authentication and role-based access controls. The OBS calibration campaign produced approximately 350 GB of broadband seismic and hydrophone data, which have been converted to daily miniSEED¹⁷ files. Together, these datasets support ongoing calibration studies, sensitivity analyses, and investigations of environmental and instrumental noise, forming a reference dataset for future DAS deployments on long-haul submarine cables.

3.3 Svalbard and Ny Ålesund

The Svalbard and Ny-Ålesund deployment represents the most complex and data-intensive configuration within SUBMERSE, integrating multiple DAS and SOP systems across two parallel 260 km submarine fibre-optic cables connecting Longyearbyen and Ny-Ålesund. The site hosts four SOP units — two Cesnet Polbox¹⁸ systems and two Novoptel PM1000¹⁹ devices—which have been operating continuously since late 2023. These systems are synchronised using White Rabbit²⁰ timing referenced to a hydrogen maser atomic clock, enabling high-precision polarimetric measurements. DAS operations commenced in 2022 with a C-band OptoDAS interrogator typically configured at an 8m gauge length and sampling rates between 200 and 625Hz, optimised over time to balance data volume and signal quality. In addition, a low-frequency L-band DAS interrogator operated between September 2024 and March 2025 to support seabed temperature and long-period sensing studies. A complementary OBS deployment in Kongsfjorden provides independent reference data to support DAS time-correction, orientation estimation, and calibration analyses.

DAS and SOP data acquired in Norway are stored and managed by Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (SIKT)²¹ and Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)²² in what might be termed a national Trusted Research Environment (TRE), with access restricted to authorised and classified personnel. SOP systems generated continuous data streams between October 2023 and September 2024, producing approximately 6–12 GB per day per unit. DAS acquisition produces data volumes of up to 7 TB per day, reflecting the scale and resolution of the deployment. From these raw datasets, approximately 20 TB of filtered DAS data have been made available to SUBMERSE partners, including curated contributions to international initiatives such as Global DAS Month. Due to stringent national security requirements, the declassification of data remains as of yet a manual to semi-automated process, after which non-sensitive datasets can be released for research use. As of December 2025, only around 80 GB of scrubbed SOP data have been approved for access by researchers. OBS data collected in Kongsfjorden will be archived through appropriate repositories once remaining metadata corrections, including timing and orientation parameters, have been finalised.

¹⁶ <https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/hdf5/>

¹⁷ <https://docs.fdsn.org/projects/miniseed3/en/latest/>

¹⁸ <https://czechlight.cesnet.cz/en/specialized-hardware/polbox/>

¹⁹ https://www.novoptel.de/Polarimeter/Polarimeter_PM1000_en.php

²⁰ <https://white-rabbit.web.cern.ch/>

²¹ <https://sikt.no/>

²² <https://www.ntnu.edu/>

3.4 Preveza - Crotone

A DAS interrogator was installed at the Preveza landing station on 25 February 2025 on an approximately 143 km dark fibre of the ISLALINK²³ submarine cable system (Ionian link). The system is configured with a 20 m gauge length, 10 m spatial sampling, and a 500 Hz sampling rate, producing 14,002 virtual channels. Full-resolution DAS data have been continuously acquired since installation and are stored locally in HDF5 format. By December 2025, the accumulated volume amounts to approximately 160 TB, stored across facilities at NOA and GFZ. In parallel, a decimated real-time data stream comprising 100 channels at 100Hz and approximately 1 km spacing is distributed to The National Observatory of Athens (NOA)²⁴ and made accessible for analysis through the EIDA infrastructure²⁵. For the spatially decimated data the FDSN temporary network code ZQ was assigned to this installation, foreseeing a wider future usage by the seismological community through EIDA node at NOA. Access to raw full-resolution data remains²⁶, after which transfer to national long-term storage is planned. Formal calibration activities are foreseen once data-sharing and operational agreements are fully in place.

Subject to successful installation, the Crotone landing station at the opposite end of the Ionian cable is expected to be instrumented at the end of January 2026. Once it is operational, it will contribute to the data collection in the Ionian Sea.

3.5 Rhodes

The Rhodes–Kos terrestrial–subsea fibre link was instrumented on 12 February 2025 as part of the SUBMERSE deployment in Greece. The DAS system was initially configured with an 8.2m gauge length, 4.08m spatial sampling, and a 500Hz sampling rate; however, significant signal attenuation was observed beyond approximately 40km, likely caused by a defective fibre segment near the landing point. As an interim mitigation measure, the system was reconfigured in July 2025 to focus on the reliable terrestrial section of the link, resulting in the acquisition of 47,000 channels over a distance of 48km. Further diagnostic investigations and formal calibration activities are planned once the underlying fibre issue is resolved.

By December 2025, the Rhodes site had generated approximately 9TB of full-resolution DAS data from the terrestrial segment, stored locally at the site. Preliminary real-time decimated data streams are currently under evaluation by the National Observatory of Athens (NOA), but no permanent distribution pathway to domain specific repositories has yet been established. Access to both raw and derived data is restricted under a non-disclosure agreement with the cable owner COSMOTE, and precise virtual receiver coordinates have not been released yet through GRNET that leases the fibre. It remains to be completed the secure connectivity to the Greek National Infrastructure for Research and Technology (GRNET)²⁷, after which transfer to national long-term storage is planned. Despite the reduced spatial coverage, the collected dataset provides valuable observations relevant to regional seismicity monitoring in the eastern Aegean region, but it might be also useful for urban monitoring applications.

²³ <https://islalink.com/>

²⁴ <https://www.noa.gr/en/>

²⁵ <https://www.orfeus-eu.org/data/eida/nodes/>

²⁶ <https://grnet.gr/en/>

²⁷ <https://grnet.gr/en/>

4 Data Access

Data access within the SUBMERSE project is structured around three interconnected components: the national Trusted Research Environment (TRE), the open buffer, and the data transfer mechanisms linking these two layers. Together, these components define how data move from the point of acquisition to controlled processing environments and, where permitted, onward to shared research infrastructures. This section describes the protocols, services, operational processes, and licensing conditions that govern data access across these components, reflecting the project's commitment to security and traceability.

4.1 Trusted Research Environment

Within the Trusted Research Environment, data access concerns the secure transfer of data from the generating instruments and acquisition systems to protected national storage facilities. This stage primarily involves raw, high-resolution DAS and SOP data that may contain sensitive information and therefore require strict access control. Data transfer is performed using standard, secure protocols such as https in the case of RClone or TCP based binary protocol in the case of Kafaka which is used in the miniseed format. Where RClone or miniseed is not used Secure File Transfer Protocol (SFTP) can be relied upon as an alternative. Transport protocols connect to APIs which are part of an S3-compatible object storage interface. Operationally, data are pushed from the interrogating devices to the designated storage locations using synchronisation tools, most commonly RClone²⁸, which enables reliable and automated data transfer and mirroring. The use of RClone is governed by its permissive MIT licence, supporting flexibility in deployment across national infrastructures. Access within the TRE is restricted to authorised personnel and systems in accordance with national policies and project security guidelines. By pushing from one interface to another, access control lists can be tightened to reduce the number of potential attack vectors, while also allowing the control over when data is released to the more secure elements in the TRE.

In the case of decimated real time streaming from specified channels and at particular frequencies, the data released by the interrogators is within boundaries deemed non-sensitive (based on an agreement with each country national authority). Currently, only the DAS interrogators have the ability to operate such a stream, due to their attached compute being capable of supporting such a stream. The streams are established using kafaka protocol and ZeroMQ, via the SeisComP plugin, which converts this data into the seedlink protocol, part of the seismology communities miniseed system. The data can then be added to the standard seismological archives and are accessible through standard EIDA services, e.g FDSN web services or the EIDA portal (EIDA European Integrated Data Archive, which is an ORFEUS facility, and a Thematic Core Services of EPOS).

4.2 Inter buffer data access

Inter buffer data access refers to the controlled movement of data between the Trusted Research Environment or data-generating sources and the open buffer, as well as the interfaces to downstream research infrastructure workflows. This component primarily supports near-real-time and real-time data streams, enabling timely processing, monitoring, and dissemination of selected, non-sensitive data products. Data exchange at this stage relies on S3-compatible interfaces for object-based transfer and on streaming technologies such as Kafka for continuous data flows. Services supporting inter-buffer access include RClone for synchronisation and transfer, Kafka-based streaming services, and miniSEED data pipelines built on Kafka for real-time seismic waveform

²⁸ <https://rclone.org/>

distribution. Access is governed by project-defined workflows and role-based permissions to ensure that only appropriately processed and authorised data enter the open buffer.

4.3 Open buffer

The open buffer provides a controlled access layer for data that have passed initial processing and security checks and are suitable for broader research use. Access to data in the open buffer is implemented through S3-compatible protocols and is provided via MinIO object storage services. At this stage, data are made available primarily for read access by eligible users, including project partners and, where applicable, external research communities. MinIO is deployed under the GNU Affero General Public License v3 (AGPL v3)²⁹, ensuring transparency and compliance with open-source principles. The open buffer acts as an intermediary between national infrastructures and long-term repositories, facilitating inspection, validation, and further processing of datasets prior to archival or publication in domain-specific repositories.

²⁹ <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/agpl-3.0.en.html>

5 Status of Use Cases

The SUBMERSE project focuses on specific use cases in Geoscience, Oceanographic and Marine Biology, detailed below. Many more potential use cases exist outside the scope of the SUBMERSE project and the data produced in the SUBMERSE project can very well be used in other use cases.

Use cases provide a practical entry point for implementing FAIR data management by grounding abstract principles in concrete scientific and operational scenarios. By developing and testing data workflows, metadata practices, access mechanisms, and governance procedures for specific use cases, the project establishes reusable and FAIR-aligned processes that can be iteratively refined. These validated workflows support long-term sustainability by enabling efficient adaptation to new sites, data types, and user communities beyond the initial use cases, reducing duplication of effort and ensuring consistency across the data lifecycle.

The use cases demonstrate how submarine fibre-optic sensing can generate new scientific insights across multiple disciplines by exploiting the unique capabilities of Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) measurements. While the project's core activities focus on establishing and operating fibre optic sensing technology, in a coherent, coordinated and interoperable manner, the use-case programme translates these technical achievements into concrete scientific applications. By bringing together these use cases, the SUBMERSE project provides a structured framework in which project partners and research communities can test analytical methods, evaluate data quality, and explore the added value of fibre-optic sensing in real-world research scenarios.

The use cases spanning the different scientific domains highlight different aspects of DAS and SOP performance. In geoscience, the focus lies on earthquake detection, magnitude estimation, phase picking, and event localisation. The SUBMERSE research partners worked on assessing how offshore fibre-optic cables can complement or extend conventional seismic networks. In oceanography, the emphasis is on monitoring marine processes, in particular surface gravity waves in shallow water DAS recordings, while the marine biology use cases focus on monitoring Baleen-whale vocalisations. Together, these activities provide a comprehensive assessment of how fibre optic sensing infrastructures can support multidisciplinary research, paving the way for future operational applications and long-term monitoring.

A key achievement of the use-case activities is the establishment of archival and real-time streaming of virtual stations, specifically tailored to the needs of the geoscientific user community. By providing data in miniSEED format and, where feasible, via real-time streaming protocols, the project aligns with established practices and expectations in seismology and related disciplines, thereby lowering barriers to uptake and reuse. These virtual station products are designed with FAIR principles in mind, ensuring consistent metadata, standardised formats, and clear provenance. At the same time, the approach incorporates the use of intentionally obfuscated metadata—particularly with respect to precise cable routes and virtual station locations—to balance scientific usability with security and regulatory constraints.

5.1 Geoscientific Use Cases

The geoscientific use cases within SUBMERSE focus on advancing the detection, characterization, and interpretation of seismic signals using distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) on submarine fibre-optic cables. A major achievement is the compilation of a benchmark DAS dataset of local earthquake recordings, drawn from 13 submarine cables worldwide across diverse tectonic settings including Alaska, Chile, Japan, and the Canary Islands, comprising nearly 92 million channels. These data are accompanied by semi-automated labelling of P and S arrivals, generated with a single channel machine learning model, followed by manual review and adjustments to ensure and improve reliability. Building on this corpus, the project has developed a submarine

DAS-specific machine-learning mode for multi-channel picking by adapting the DeepLabV3 image-segmentation architecture, enabling robust automatic phase identification in offshore environments.

A key question for the project has been whether machine-learning pickers trained on terrestrial data can generalise to the virtual stations sparsely distributed along offshore DAS, e.g., every kilometre in the case of the Preveza cable, as these data are readily available at seismic data centres through real-time miniseed format. Tests using several pre-trained models including PhaseNet³⁰ DiTing³¹ highlight that for larger events these generally work well, but performance depends on preprocessing choices, such as converting the strain-rate data to velocity and resampling to 100Hz, the sampling rate for which these pickers were trained. Among the tested models, DiTing has shown the most accurate P- and S-phase picks on single channel offshore velocity data. Beyond picking, the team has also investigated local magnitude estimation using DAS, implementing a workflow that converts strain-rate measurements to displacement through spatial integration and subsequently applies the Wood–Anderson transfer function. Magnitudes are then computed using a Greek local-magnitude relation based on peak-to-trough amplitudes, with preliminary results showing good agreement with reference seismic catalogues.

These results demonstrate that, with appropriate data preparation and model selection, standard earthquake analysis workflows can be applied effectively to offshore DAS installations.

The geoscience work package has also experimented with back projection-based event location methods tailored for virtual station arrays of DAS data. By transforming and back projecting characteristic functions such as Kurtosis statistical analysis, the team is evaluating whether distributed subarrays can enhance the signal-to-noise ratio and support near-real-time offshore earthquake location.

As an unexpected outcome, serendipitous DAS recordings of T-phases (tertiary waves) at the GeOLAB site from a nearby local earthquake, have provided valuable insight into their generation mechanism. T-phases are acoustic waves travelling in the Sound Fixing And Ranging (SOFAR) channel, a low velocity layer in the stratified water column, which have been converted from elastic waves triggered by an earthquake. The SUBMERSE recordings represent, to our knowledge, the only near field recordings of T-phases. From a consideration of travel times, it appears likely that the T waves are generated by interaction of the elastic wave with a chain of seamounts between the DAS cable and the earthquake.

5.2 Oceanographic Use Cases

Beyond geophysics, SUBMERSE investigates how DAS can contribute to physical oceanography by evaluating its sensitivity to near-shore and shelf-sea processes. Initial validation has focused on the Preveza site, where DAS observations are being compared against traditional oceanographic instrumentation. Planning is underway for the deployment of an Acoustic Wave and Current Profiler (AWAC) by the end of 2025, supported by the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)³²/POSEIDON³³. The instrument is placed in shallow waters (<30m) to simplify deployment without requiring a research vessel, although this introduces heightened risks due to intense fishing activity. Data will be collected in delayed mode, since near-real-time streaming is not cost-effective at present. Parallel work includes using Theoretical Dispersion Curve (TDC) fitting to extract information on wave incidence angles, significant wave height, and tidal modulation from DAS recordings of ocean surface gravity waves, which dominate the signal for shallow seafloor. Already analysis of a seven-day test data set

³⁰ <https://github.com/AI4EPS/PhaseNet>

³¹ Zhao, Ming, Xiao Zhuowei, and Shi Chen. "DiTing-IoT: deep-learning-enabled real-time seismic data processing via edge and cloud computing." AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts. Vol. 2022. 2022.

³² <https://www.hcmr.gr/en/>

³³ <https://poseidon.hcmr.gr/>

demonstrates the excellent correspondence between TDC-derived parameters and independent oceanographic observations, supporting the viability of DAS for monitoring coastal hydrodynamics. Funding has already been secured to deploy an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler in shallow water at the Madeira site in order to calibrate DAS data for use as a proxy for sea state.

5.3 Marine Biology Use Cases

The third use case focuses on marine bioacoustics, where DAS offers the unprecedented ability to monitor Baleen whales over large coastal and basin-scale distances. The GeoLab cable has already recorded Fin, Blue, and Sei whale vocalisations, alongside unidentified low-frequency signals. To build robust detection and localisation algorithms, SUBMERSE is developing automated workflows based on representative, high-quality training data. Because manual selection of samples proved inefficient, a first-stage detector was developed using band-limited energy and matched-filter cross-correlation, tuned to the 20 Hz Fin-whale note. When applied to a day with known whale activity, this detector identified more than 69,000 potential events across the cable. Subsequent manual validation confirmed accurate detections at selected distances, while some near-shore channels showed high false-positive rates requiring further refinement. Ongoing work focuses on localising calls using time delays between channels, expanding detection strategies to additional species, and ultimately quantifying seasonal and spatial patterns of whale activity. These insights will inform ecological research and potentially support local management practices such as whale-watching guidelines.

6 FAIR Data in the SUBMERSE project

The SUBMERSE project aims for its research data to be managed according to the FAIR principles—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—while recognising that the project operates within strict national security frameworks and with heterogeneous data collection environments. The ambition to implement the FAIR principles as far as possible, is not so much due to the need to follow the Horizon Europe requirement but arises from the understanding that good data management and adherence to the FAIR principles is needed to pursue the scientific agendas of the involved communities. This is considered an evolving process of FAIRification³⁴. As a result, the degree of FAIR implementation varies across sites and data types, particularly for raw and potentially sensitive DAS and SOP data. This chapter describes the overarching FAIR strategy for the SUBMERSE project and highlights site-specific considerations where they materially affect FAIR compliance. Although not all data can nor should be made fully FAIR, SUBMERSE is committed to advancing FAIRness through progressive metadata harmonisation, DOI assignment for publishable datasets, the adoption of community standards, and the establishment of workflows that allow scrubbed data to enter trusted community repositories – in due cause automated and in real-time.

6.1 Making Data Findable (F)

The findability of SUBMERSE data relies on data repositories belonging to the research communities; their national research infrastructure provider organisations; research institutions or otherwise. Findability relies on these repositories systematic use of persistent identifiers (PID's), harmonised metadata, metadata templates. The aim is to build a workflow for the – automated – deposit of publishable data products in recognised community repositories such as EIDA. For seismic and DAS-derived products, metadata descriptions follow the DAS-RCN³⁵ recommendations and are typically encoded in StationXML when data are prepared for repository submission. Where possible, datasets are assigned PID's or Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to support citation, discovery, and long-term traceability.

Project-wide strategy

- Data products will be deposited in domain repositories where DOIs and standard metadata workflows are automatically supported.
- Each site applies internal naming conventions and metadata capture procedures to ensure that raw or restricted data remain traceable throughout the internal data lifecycle, even when not publicly findable; while primarily supporting internal governance, this homogeneity also facilitates rapid understanding and comparability across sites for external collaborators and research infrastructures, and provides a foundation that can be harmonised into common conventions or standards as data are progressively exposed and FAIRified.
- Each site applies its Data Policies hence adhering to security and data deletion policies.
- Metadata completeness aims to meet repository and community requirements.

Site-specific considerations

- **Sines:** The datasets are partially FAIR. Findability is currently internal, using dataset naming conventions, campaign identifiers, acquisition dates, and cable-segment tags. Public findability will depend on post-project agreements with ASN and EllaLink.

³⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/fairification-process/>

³⁵ <https://github.com/DAS-RCN/awesome-das>

- **Madeira:** Data have been assigned to a temporary FDSN network code (3X) for 2023. A 7 TB dataset archived at GEOFON already carries a DOI and will be publicly available from 1 January 2026 under CC BY-SA 4.0, with full StationXML metadata. A second network code was minted for the continuous SEEDLINK stream to IPMA, where it is stored.
- **Svalbard & Ny-Ålesund:** Raw data cannot yet be made findable until automated or semi-automated declassification workflows are more developed. Metadata exists but cannot be openly exposed until declassification is complete. Building an operational framework for attribution and declassification is a key priority.
- **Preveza & Rhodes:** Decimated MiniSEED channels (100 channels) have an assigned DOI but are not yet FAIR, as metadata completeness and repository-standard documentation require further work.

6.2 Making Data Accessible (A)

Accessibility in SUBMERSE is constrained by national legislation, security-classified raw data, and agreements with NREN's, cable owners and equipment providers. As a result, access to raw data is restricted, while scrubbed and processed datasets – data products – intended for scientific reuse are, to a modest extent, already being and will further be made accessible through community repositories following the repositories access policies.

Project-wide strategy

- Raw data remain within the respective national infrastructures and are not publicly accessible, as outlined in the respective Data Policies.
- Scrubbed data products will be made accessible via domain-specific repositories, currently primarily the EIDA nodes.
- Access to restricted data for validation or quality control is provided to project partners through secure authentication systems (e.g., S3-based controlled access, institutional AAI systems).
- Licensing will be applied in alignment with repository guidelines and ownership rules.

Site-specific considerations

- **Sines:** Access is currently limited to project partners through controlled MinIO S3 access. Wider accessibility depends on post-project agreements with the cable owner EllaLink and the DAS owner ASN.
- **Madeira:** The acquired GEOFON dataset will become publicly accessible in 2026 under CC BY-SA 4.0. The remaining data is limited to project partners through the INESC TEC MinIO S3 storage. The channels streamed to IPMA will be made available through EIDA at a later date.
- **Svalbard & Ny-Ålesund:** Accessibility is limited because raw data contain potentially sensitive information. Accessibility will increase only once declassification workflows are operational.
- **Preveza & Rhodes:** Local storage of decimated channels exists, but public accessibility is not enabled and requires metadata improvement and repository submission.

Overall, accessibility across SUBMERSE remains strongly shaped by national security requirements and the need to scrub sensitive information before any data can enter the public domain. Furthermore, repository submission presumes not only defined quality data product but also producing them in a meaningful and – for the wider research community – persistent manner. However, single data sets have been published as base documentation for specific scientific articles.

6.3 Making Data Interoperable (I)

Interoperability is achieved primarily through the use of community-standard file formats (HDF5, miniSEED), metadata schemes (DAS-RCN), and established domain repositories (e.g. EIDA nodes). SUBMERSE applies consistent conversion practices to ensure that downstream data products can be integrated into seismological, oceanographic, or bioacoustics workflows.

Project-wide strategy

- File formats: HDF5 is used for raw/subsampled DAS data; MiniSEED is used for down-sampled or seismic products; StationXML³⁶ is used for metadata.
- Metadata standards: SUBMERSE follows DAS-RCN metadata guidelines and aligns with EPOS/EIDA requirements where applicable.
- Repository integration: For data entering EIDA, interoperability requirements are automatically enforced through ingestion pipelines.
- Cross-domain alignment: Work is ongoing to harmonise SOP and polarimeter metadata with formats familiar to seismology and oceanography communities.

Site-specific considerations

- **Sines:** Core data stored in HDF5 already comply with standard machine-readable practices.
- **Madeira:** Raw data is stored in HDF5, complying with standard machine-readable practices. MiniSEED and StationXML standards are used for the GEOFON dataset.
- **Svalbard & Ny-Ålesund:** Interoperability is limited by the absence of fully processed and declassified outputs but remains technically feasible once processing workflows are finalised.
- **Preveza & Rhodes:** MiniSEED export is used, but metadata completeness needs improvement to achieve full interoperability.

6.4 Making Data Reusable (R)

Reusability within SUBMERSE depends on licensing, thorough documentation, clear provenance, and transparent processing steps. While raw data are restricted, scrubbed and processed data products provided via repositories will be reusable under community standards.

Project-wide strategy

Data made public will carry open licences (e.g., CC BY) whenever permitted by cable owners and national authorities.

Provenance information including processing steps, scrubbing procedures, and any applied ML models will be included in metadata or accompanying documentation.

Quality-control processes prior to release ensure that datasets meet scientific standards.

Documentation from training materials, software repositories, and data-flow diagrams supports future reuse by external researchers.

Site-specific considerations

³⁶ <https://docs.fdsn.org/projects/stationxml/en/latest/>

- **Sines:** Reuse is currently possible only within project partners. Broader reuse depends on permissions from the DAS owner ASN and the cable owner EllaLink.
- **Madeira:** The GEOFON dataset will be fully reusable under CC BY-SA 4.0 with complete metadata. Subsets of data collected from 2024 onwards will be progressively released in full-resolution or decimated form according to the publication schedule of scientific communications.
- **Svalbard & Ny-Ålesund:** Reusability hinges on establishing robust workflows for declassifying raw data and generating FAIR-compliant products.
- **Preveza & Rhodes:** Existing datasets require further documentation and metadata enhancement before they can be considered reusable in external research.

6.5 SUBMERSE data FAIRification Conclusions

The FAIR principles provide a methodological framework for sound data stewardship, focusing on the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of data, but they do not prescribe levels of openness, public exposure, or unrestricted access. FAIRification can therefore be applied independently of Open Access policies or security constraints. In the context of SUBMERSE, datasets may be extensively FAIRified—well described, persistently identified (e.g. through DOIs), and technically accessible—while remaining subject to strict access controls, licensing conditions, or national and international security regulations. The project’s approach is to implement FAIR principles as fully as possible within these constraints, ensuring that data are structured, documented, interoperable, and reusable for authorised users, even where broad or public access is not permissible.

FAIR compliance across SUBMERSE is, therefore, uneven, due to security restrictions in line with, national data policies. It has more to do with to what extent the use case research groups have been working with FAIRification, especially applying working with and standardization of controlled metadata vocabularies, standard file and data record systems. Hence, the uneven FAIR compliance is more due to the novelty of DAS/SOP data workflows. Nevertheless, the project has established a clear roadmap toward improved FAIRness by adopting community standards, assigning DOIs to publishable datasets, integrating with established repositories, and prioritising the development of frameworks for safe release of declassified data. As the instrument matures and automated scrubbing and declassification improve, the share of data that can be made openly FAIR will increase, ensuring long-term scientific value and alignment with open-science principles.

7 Other Research Outputs

In addition to the data products generated throughout the project, SUBMERSE has produced a range of complementary outputs that contribute to the project’s scientific, technical, and educational impact. These outputs include software tools that enable data processing, machine-learning applications, and operational workflows; training materials that support the diverse communities engaged with DAS and SOP data; and a growing body of scientific publications demonstrating early results and methodological advances. Together, these outputs enhance the usability, reproducibility, and long-term value of SUBMERSE data and provide the foundation for continued development and uptake of the project’s research instrument.

7.1 Training Materials

The SUBMERSE project has placed strong emphasis on building comprehensive training materials that support the diverse groups involved in the development, operation, and scientific exploitation of submarine DAS and SOP data. LifeWatch ERIC³⁷, using its established Moodle platform, is prepared to host these training resources and ensure long-term accessibility. Training needs have been systematically mapped across stakeholder groups: technicians and developers require detailed documentation and technical guidance; submarine cable vendors, network providers, and national authorities need targeted information on system operation, data handling, and security; partner staff and data stewards require training in data-lifecycle management and FAIR principles; and scientific communities need instruction on how to access, interpret, and analyse DAS and SOP data. To address these needs, SUBMERSE has already delivered internal and external training sessions—both online (December 2024) and in person at the IASPEI Early Career Scientist School (August 2025)—covering the fundamentals of DAS and SOP acquisition and processing.

Building on this foundation, three structured training modules have been proposed:

- (1) **Infrastructure, Reproducibility, and Sustainability**, including infrastructure design, equipment setup and maintenance, sensing matrix optimisation, data-flow configuration, and procedures for handling sensitive data;
- (2) **Data Lifecycle Management**, with a focus on project-wide data strategy and enabling FAIR-compliant workflows; and
- (3) **Scientific Applications**, presenting use cases in geology/seismology, oceanography, and marine biology.

Next steps include validating and finalising the module structure, appointing authors, providers, and reviewers, and converting the in-person DAS/SOP training sessions into asynchronous digital modules with persistent access to example datasets and analysis notebooks. Additional activities are planned, such as OptoDAS setup training tailored to specific use cases and a joint training event with Blue-Cloud 2026³⁸. These efforts will ensure that SUBMERSE leaves behind a sustainable, usable training ecosystem that supports broad uptake of the project’s methodologies and data products.

7.2 Software

In addition to the physical data collection infrastructure, SUBMERSE has produced a range of software outputs that support data analysis, anomaly detection, and monitoring across the distributed fibre-optic sensing network. A central component is a Python-based software framework designed to streamline anomaly detection in DAS data using machine-learning methods. The software enables partners to train their own models by supplying

³⁷ <https://www.lifewatch.eu/>

³⁸ <https://blue-cloud.org/>

datasets of raw files and associated labels, as demonstrated successfully by the Svalbard installation, where labelled events were available. Complementing these capabilities is a suite of classical signal-processing tools, including Fourier transforms, band-pass filtering, and other methods used to inspect, clean, and characterise both DAS and SOP data. An optional dashboard provides visualisation and basic monitoring of anomaly detections in near-real time; while this dashboard is not production-grade, it serves as a useful prototype for partners evaluating deployment options and workflow integration.

The software is currently hosted privately on the PCSS GitLab instance³⁹, with access managed internally within the project. Although the system is still under active development, the intention is to open-source the codebase once it reaches a stable state. Only code will be released publicly; trained machine-learning models will remain internal due to their dependence on site-specific datasets and potential security constraints. Since all relevant datasets will be published independently by the responsible partners, the software release does not raise data-sharing or provenance concerns. Partners may request deployment of the software on their own hardware environments, such as interrogators or dedicated virtual machines, and work is ongoing to enable operational use at the Sines site.

Several developments remain in progress. Initial efforts to integrate machine-learning approaches for SOP anomaly detection were constrained by the limited availability of SOP datasets, and work will resume once additional replay data is provided by national partners. In parallel, the project is exploring the development of an unsupervised anomaly detection model that does not require labelled training data. Such a model would allow the software to be deployed more easily across different cables without retraining; however, early tests demonstrate that models trained on Svalbard data perform well only on that specific cable system, underscoring the complexity of generalising across heterogeneous fibre environments. Finally, the team is refining and reorganising the software to improve usability for researchers without deep programming expertise, broadening its potential uptake as an analytical tool within the wider SUBMERSE and EPOS communities.

7.3 Scientific Publications

The scientific output of SUBMERSE includes a broad range of publications that reflect both foundational research and applied developments within the project. Classic peer-reviewed papers document advances in DAS and SOP methodologies, signal processing techniques, and scientific use cases across geoscience and oceanography. In addition, the project has produced a dataset publication that makes a curated subset of SUBMERSE data openly available for community use, as well as software-publications that provide tools and workflows developed during the project. Together, these publications demonstrate the scientific maturity of the SUBMERSE instrument and provide essential resources for further research and reuse.

7.4 Data emerging from Project Management

In terms of Project Management, some data will be collected and securely stored for internal project use only. Data will be stored in secure folders of the coordinator office accessing it (EFIS Centre). This includes contacts and emails from the consortium partners' teams, the Policy and Security Advisory Board— who will have access to a common mailing list. For logistic purposes, the communication lead partner (GEANT) has also access to the lists as manager of the mailing lists through SYMPA system.

³⁹ <https://gitlab.pcss.pl/explore/projects>

Project management data may also include descriptive and administrative data related to participation to project events (meetings, trainings, final event, etc.) and primarily entails participant lists (name, last name, organisation if applicable, country and email).

Overall, project management related data have a limited size <1GB including mailing list files as well as registration lists and attendance reports.

Concerning data security, all project management data collected content is archived in a secure manner, via regular database backups, in the project's collaborative platforms (server located in the EU) that will serve as the main backup area. Preservation and back-ups of the data are ensured by the EFIS Centre data centre preservation policies: daily backups, security updates, securely controlled administrative access.

8 Data Security

Data security remains a critical pillar of the SUBMERSE project, as submarine telecommunication fibres can inadvertently capture information considered sensitive by national authorities. Although SUBMERSE pursues strictly scientific objectives, raw DAS and SOP data may contain dual-use signals, such as vessel traffic signatures or infrastructure-related patterns. To address this, the project operates within a robust security framework aligned with recognised international and European standards, including ISO/IEC 27001 control principles and, where applicable, obligations arising from the NIS2 directive. Compliance is documented through regular reviews of the status.

Security governance is coordinated through Task 1.3 (Ethics and Security), supported by the project's Security Advisory Board, which provides guidance on sensitive data handling, scrubbing procedures, access control, and risk assessment. Due to their sensitive content, the deliverables produced under these activities are not publicly available.

To accommodate national security concerns and at the same time maintain maximum FAIRness of the data generated, a model for active involvement of the security agencies is used in SUBMERSE. The overarching approach follows the security architecture described in the SUBMERSE white paper, which adopts a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) model. In the following paragraphs, the key principles of using the TRE Framework are described.

Within the framework, raw data remains confined to the country of origin and are processed under national security policies before any non-sensitive derivatives are released for scientific use. Raw DAS and SOP data are stored only temporarily — typically for no longer than three months—within secure national NREN-operated facilities. During this buffering period, data undergo mandatory scrubbing to remove sensitive information in accordance with site-specific and nationally agreed procedures. After scrubbing, raw data are deleted unless extended retention is required by national law or security authorities. Only the scrubbed, FAIRified datasets are preserved for long-term use and transferred to disciplinary repositories, which apply their own preservation, backup, and access policies. SUBMERSE itself does not maintain backups of raw data; backup and replication apply exclusively to datasets that have passed security clearance.

Access to data is tightly controlled and logged throughout the data lifecycle. Logs are designed to be immutable or tamper-evident and are readily available if required for audit or incident investigation. Incident response procedures are in place, defining clear roles and responsibilities for the involved staff, with breach triage initiated within 24 hours and eventual GDPR notification timelines respected. Regular incident response exercises are conducted to validate readiness and capture lessons learned.

Vendor and service provider security is addressed through structured assurance processes, including security questionnaires, penetration-testing attestations where applicable, and transparency regarding subcontractors. Identified risks associated with external providers are documented in a maintained risk register, with assigned owners and mitigation actions. A structured approach to e.g. Cable Operators based on internationally recognized standards is essential with the increasing focus on Fiber Cables as critical infrastructure in accordance with e.g. NIS2 (reference)

Access to raw or high-resolution data is thereby limited to authorised personnel and, in some cases, restricted to controlled computing environments to prevent unauthorised export. Scrubbed datasets are released openly once validated, although certain metadata elements — such as precise virtual receiver coordinates—may remain generalised to comply with security requirements. This layered and standards-aligned security strategy ensures that SUBMERSE maximises scientific value while fully respecting the legal, ethical, and security constraints inherent to fibre-optic sensing of operational telecommunication infrastructure.

Depending on local conditions, the SUBMERSE sites have developed and implemented a locally viable model to handle the dialogue and cooperation with local authorities and national agencies.

9 SUBMERSE Ethics

Ethical considerations in the SUBMERSE project are addressed in close coordination with Task 1.3 (Ethics and Security), which provides detailed internal analyses, procedures, and guidance. While the full ethics and security reports produced under this task are not publicly available due to their sensitive nature, the present Data Management Plan summarises the key ethical principles and practices that govern data acquisition, handling, and dissemination within the project.

SUBMERSE data collection activities are conducted for the purpose of public-interest scientific research. The lawful basis for data processing is documented at national level in accordance with applicable legislation and institutional requirements. Where formal ethics approvals are not mandated under existing national frameworks, the relevant national government authorities have nonetheless been informed of deployment activities and data acquisition plans. This ensures transparency, accountability, and alignment with national oversight expectations, even in cases where no explicit permitting process applies.

Ethical governance also encompasses data residency and international data transfer considerations. As a general principle, data are stored and processed within the country where they are generated, in line with national regulations, security requirements, and infrastructure ownership agreements. Cross-border data transfers outside the EU/EEA are not foreseen within the scope of the project. Should such transfers become necessary in exceptional cases, they would be subject to the involvement and approval of the hosting site and would rely on appropriate legal safeguards, such as the European Commission's standard contractual clauses or equivalent mechanisms.

The technologies being developed in SUBMERSE, may be used within a number of scenarios that have clear ethical impacts. They may e.g. be used for detecting illegal fishing activities, thereby contributing to the protection of endangered species. Also for protecting sub-sea or seabed environment through detection of illegal mining or scraping of the seabed. To enable local authorities using FOS-data for these juridical purposes, imposes very strict adoption of e.g. the FAIR principles.

Overall, SUBMERSE adopts a precautionary and responsible approach to ethics, ensuring that scientific innovation based on submarine fibre-optic sensing is pursued in a manner that respects legal frameworks, national sovereignty, institutional responsibilities, and broader societal expectations.

10 SUBMERSE outlook and final remarks

Looking ahead, SUBMERSE partners will continue refining data workflows, enhancing long-term preservation strategies, and preparing the instrument for sustained scientific use beyond the project's lifetime. This will be done in a mix of individual sites data policies and practices as well as a consortium coordinated follow-up strategy.

- At the Madeira site, future work will focus on automated event and whale-call detection, enabling selective retention of full-resolution DAS data around relevant acoustic or seismic signals. The EIDA node operated by IPMA is committed to continue to acquire and archive a subset of channels (virtual stations) streamed in real-time through the seedlink protocol to be distributed as miniseed data.
- At the Svalbard and Ny-Ålesund sites, further development of the envisioned multi-stakeholder “sensing data factory” will require dedicated long-term funding and multidisciplinary expertise, as the anticipated user landscape spans diverse agencies and research domains with varying data and product needs.
- For the Preveza and Rhodes installations, NOAA and GFZ will continue to retain locally whatever data are necessary and feasible to support future analyses. Based on current resources, DAS recording at Crotone (opposite end of Crotone-Preveza cable) will only be possible until the end of the project in April 2026. Decimated data (virtual stations) miniseed are made available through EPOS-EIDA nodes (NOA for Preveza side; tbd for Crotone).
- At the Sines site, long-term data collection remains dependent on decisions by the cable owner (EllaLink) and the DAS provider (ASN); nevertheless, INESC TEC will preserve SUBMERSE project data in its MinIO S3 repository for continued scientific use in accordance with institutional policies and partner agreements. Should acquisition cease, efforts will shift to maintaining curated and well-documented datasets to safeguard their research value. Decimated data (virtual stations) are made available through IPMA EIDA node.
- Collaborative and extensive efforts to develop jointly accepted automation and ML/AI-based classification and declassification of raw data will contribute substantially to increase throughput and reduce latency through the TRE, and should therefore be focus in any potential following project. NRENs are in a good position to provide the secure network and high-performance computing resources. A TRE will probably be needed/requested in every country as awareness of the potential of fibre optic sensing develops.

Across all sites, these forward-looking activities underscore the commitment to sustaining the scientific, technical, and societal benefits of SUBMERSE beyond the project's formal end.

A.3 Rhodes

A.4 Sines

